

Research Guide

Overall Theme and Structure

The overall project is titled “Examining ACG Culture within Engels’s ‘Monogamy–Prostitution’ Framework” and is divided into three chapters: (1) theoretical groundwork and contemporary extensions; (2) a critique of the mechanisms and viewing logics of non-adult content; and (3) a critique of the mechanisms and viewing logics of adult animated content (Hentai). A separate section of “References and Notes” accompanies the three chapters.

Part 1 Engels’s ‘Family–Prostitution’ Double Mechanism (Theory and Contemporary Extensions) — Chapter Abstract

This chapter rereads *The Origin of the Family, Private Property and the State*, starting from the idea that “monogamy–prostitution” are two poles of the same mechanism. Combining Marx’s concepts of “commodity fetishism/objectification,” it argues that when sex is abstracted from social relations and given a price and circulation, women are transformed into commodities that can be possessed. The text also examines the limits of Engels’s account (such as the naturalization of heterosexuality and of women “giving themselves”), and introduces feminist critiques of women’s symbolization/de-subjectification within kinship–exchange structures. Turning to the present, the chapter uses the governance of offline prostitution and online platforms such as OnlyFans to show structural constraints such as unequal income distribution, lock-in by platforms and payment chains, privacy risks and the burden of emotional labour, and high exit costs, demonstrating how “sexual commodification” continues in more concealed forms. The chapter ends by opening the question toward the ACG field, setting up the starting point for the next chapter.

Keywords: OnlyFans; sexual commodification; commodity fetishism; emotional labour; monogamy–prostitution.

Part 2 A Critique of Non-Adult Anime and the ‘Second-Dimension Game’ Ecology — Chapter Abstract

This chapter focuses on the “non-adult content” segment. It first sketches differences in age ratings between TV anime/mobile games versus console games and platforms, and points out that “no visible nudity ≠ no problem.” The core argument is an industrialized mechanism of attribute collaging–scarcity-based selling–identificatory interpellation: using “moe attributes” to break down female figures into combinable external/character “tags,” and commodifying them as triggers for consumption; character design follows a pipeline of “concept first–attaching elements–then narrativizing,” with external sexualized components flexibly swapped in and out for events and collaborations. In parallel, male protagonists are de-featured and hollowed out to facilitate audience self-insertion. Drawing on Althusser’s notion of interpellation, the chapter

shows how forms of address such as “Commander/Teacher/Master” position the player as a dominating subject; with Goffman's concepts of “face” and “line,” it explains the ongoing performance required once this identification is taken up. The chapter concludes by summarizing an “individual–identity–script” loop: players are positioned as dominators → they act according to pre-written scripts → the dominating identity is reproduced. Non-adult content likewise consolidates unequal relations of looking within a more “purely” commodified chain.

Keywords: ACG culture; moe; moe attributes; objectification; interpellation; para-interaction; face; line.

Part 3 A Critique of Adult Animated Content (Hentai) — Chapter Abstract

This chapter first outlines the legal and self-regulatory trajectory of “obscene materials” in Japan (Article 175 of the Penal Code, relevant case law, and industry regulation), and compares it with restrictions on “extreme pornography/rape depictions” in the UK, US, and elsewhere, in order to highlight the relatively loose thematic boundaries under Japan's “adults-only” classification. It then uses cases such as *Densha no Ōkami* (RapeLay) to show how “sexual offences as core gameplay/narrative” become problematic and circulate in public controversy; through sampling of site-front titles with multiple rounds of refreshing, it points out the high proportion of content in the sample centred on male sexual domination and female non-consent. To explain why such viewing can persist, the chapter proposes and threads together four “rings”: spectacularization (Debord), kawaii-ization (Ngai), moral disengagement (Bandura), and sexual scripts (Simon & Gagnon). The conclusion is that viewing does not equal committing acts, but along the chain of “spectacle–cuteness–moral exemption–script consolidation,” the logic of domination is aestheticized and normalized; the virtual is not harmless.

Keywords: adult animation (Hentai); adult games; depictions of sexual offences; sexual domination; spectacularization; kawaii-ization; moral disengagement; sexual script(s).